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**PREOPERATIVE CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL RESULTS OF OPERATIVE
TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH VARUS DEFORMING OSTEOARTHRITIS OF THE
KNEE JOINT WITH ARTHROSCOPIC DEBRIDEMENT AND PROXIMAL FIBULAR
OSTEOTOMY COMPLEX**

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6559231>

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the study of preoperative clinical, radiological outcomes of 70 patients with varus deformity of the knee joint deforming osteoarthritis who underwent arthroscopic debridement and proximal fibular osteotomy. For the purpose of surgical intervention, arthroscopic debridement and proximal fibular osteotomy were performed.

Keywords: knee joint, deforming osteoarthritis, arthroscopic treatment, osteotomy of the proximal fibula.

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ПРЕДОПЕРАЦИОННЫЕ КЛИНИКО-РАДИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ОПЕРАТИВНОГО ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С ВАРУСНО-ДЕФОРМИРУЮЩИМ ОСТЕОАРТРИТОМ КОЛЕННОГО СУСТАВА С АРТРОСКОПИЧЕСКОЙ ДЕБРИДМЕНТИЕЙ И КОМПЛЕКСОМ ПРОКСИМАЛЬНОЙ ФИБУЛЯРНОЙ ОСТЕОТОМИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена изучению дооперационных клинико-рентгенологических исходов у 70 пациентов с варусной деформацией коленного сустава с деформирующим остеоартрозом, которым была выполнена артроскопическая обработка раны и проксимальная остеотомия малоберцовой кости. С целью оперативного вмешательства проведены артроскопический дебридемент и проксимальная фибулярная остеотомия.

Ключевые слова: коленный сустав, деформирующий остеоартроз, артроскопическая обработка, остеотомия проксимального отдела малоберцовой кости.

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ARTROSKOPIK DEBRIDEMENT VA PROKSIMAL FIBULYAR OSTEOTOMIYA KOMPLEKS QO'LLANILGAN TIZZA BO'G'IMI VARUSLI DEFORMASIYALOVCHI OSTEoarTRITI BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLAR OPERATIV DAVOSIDAN OLDINGI KLINIK, RENTGENOLOGIK NATIJALARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu makola artroskopik debridement va proksimal fibulyar osteotomiya amaliyoti bajarilgan tizza bo'g'imi deformasiyalovchi osteoartriti varusli deformasiyasi bilan og'rigan 70 nafar bemorlarning amaliyotdan oldingi klinik, rentgenologik natijalarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan. Jarrohlik amaliyoti sifatida artroskopik debridement va proksimal fibulyar osteotomiya amaliyoti bajarilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: tizza bo'g'imi, deformatsiyalanuvchi osteoartrit, artroskopiya, osteotomiyaning proksimal fibulari.

Introduction:

Degenerative-dystrophic lesions of the knee joint have the highest rate among the joints of the musculoskeletal system [1,3,4].

V. I. Tropin and et al. (2016) reported that degenerative-dystrophic changes of the internal structure of the joint, concussion of the upper part of the humerus, varicose veins of the upper part of the hip joint, are the main causes of pain syndrome in patients with osteoarthritis of the knee joint (DOA). In those cases, the medial part of the knee joint is often damaged [2,6,7].

V.D. Makushin and O.K. When Chegurov (2007) conducted an ultrasound examination of 87 patients (95 joints) with varicose veins of the knee joint and found thickening of the medial surface of the knee, the occurrence of lateral exostoses, radiographs of 74 patients with varus of the knee joint showed a geometric change in the medial diameter of the calf bone by an average of 3-8 mm and decentralization of the interstitial tumor biomechanical axis was detected in 30 patients.

Decentralization of the axis of the joint surface and more than 11° deviations from the calf area and frontal instability in the capsule and lumbar apparatus were detected in 67 patients [5,8].

Research objectives:

To study of clinical and instrumental results of preoperative treatment of patients with varus deforming osteoarthritis of the knee joint using a complex of arthroscopic debridement and proximal fibular osteotomy.

Materials and methods:

In our research, we covered 70 (59 women and 11 men) patients aged 35 to 80 years old with varus deformities of the knee treated in the Department of Sports Trauma of the Republican Specialized Scientific Center of Traumatology and Orthopedics in 2019-2021. Preoperative outcomes were studied in all patients. (Table 1)

Table 1

Distribution of patients by gender and age

Groups	Age Gender	35-44	45-59	60-80
Main group n= 70	Male n=11	1	6	4
	Female n=59	4	35	20
Total 70		5	41	24

As can be seen from Table 1, the deforming osteoarthritis incidence of knee joint was highest in the 45-59 age group (n=41). In this regard, in our gender analysis, there were 59 women and 11 men. The lowest rates were observed in 5 patients in the 1st age group (35-44 years).

Findings:

The main symptom of the deforming osteoarthritis of the knee joint is pain, and the intensity of pain in these patients was assessed on a "visual-analog scale" (VAS) scale. Pain syndrome was assessed on a VAS scale in patients with preoperative, postoperative first 6/24/48/72 hours and 3,6 months postoperative on a 10-point scale. (Table 2)

Table 2

Assessment of pain intensity on a 10-point VAS scale relative to the degree of degenerative process in patients with varus deformity osteoarthritis of the knee joint.

Point Level of DOA	VAS scale n=70										
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	No pain	Light pain	Mild pain	Severe pain		Very severe pain		Unbearable pain			
2 nd Level DOA (n=32)	-	5 (7,1%) (1,1±0,3)	7 (10%) (3,2±0,6)	12 (17,1%) (5,1±0,7)		8 (11,4%) (7,2±0,4)		-			
3 rd Level DOA (n=20)	-	-	7 (10%) (3,8±0,9)	11 (15,8%) (5,8±0,6)		1 (1,4%) (8,4±0,7)		1 (1,4%) (9,4±0,6)			
knee joint flexion contracture (n=18)	-	-	2 (2,9%) (4,6±0,4)	6 (8,6%) (6,7±0,8)		6 (8,6%) (8,8±0,4)		4 (5,7%) (9,8±0,7)			
Total	-	5 (7,1%)	16 (22,9%)	29 (41,5%)		15 (21,4%)		5 (7,1%)			
P	-	-	<0,001	<0,002		<0,01		<0,01			

Note: p<0,01 - <0,001

When we analyzed the data in Table 2, we found that 29 (41.5%) patients had a high intensity of pain with a high degree of confidence in most cases of "severe pain" and in rare cases, 5 (7.1%) patients were diagnosed with "mild pain" and "unbearable pain" criteria (p<0,01 - <0,001).

In osteoarthritis of the knee joint with varus deformity, the intensity of pain is directly proportional to the depth of the degenerative process in the knee joint and “Mild pain” with high reliability in DOA II - 5 (7.1%) patients, “moderate pain” in DOA III - 7 (10%) and “severe pain” - 11 (15.8%) patients was identified. The intensity of pain of "severe pain" and "very severe pain" - 6 (8.6%) and "unbearable pain" - 4 (5.7%) patients were observed in the DOA with flexion contracture of the knee joint.

The manifestation of clinical signs of the disease in varus deforming osteoarthritis of the knee joint is accompanied by functional changes in the knee joint. In this regard, clinical and functional changes in all 70 major groups of patients were analyzed using the Knee Society Score (KSS) (Insall J. et al, 1989) scale (Table 3).

Table 3
Clinical and functional assessment of varus deformity osteoarthritis of the knee joint on the KSS scale

Criteria			Patients of the main group (n=70)					
Clinical evaluation	Pain	Walking	No pain	Weak pain	Moderate pain	Acute pain		
			- (-%)	5 (7,1%)	54 (77,2%)	11 (15,7%)		
		Climbing the stairs	No pain	Weak pain	Moderate pain	Acute pain		
			- (-%)	9 (13%)	57 (81%)	4 (6%)		
	Action vintage.		5 gr.	10 gr.	15 gr.	20 gr.	25 gr.	
			2 (2,9%)	11 (15,7 %)	34 (48,6 %)	15 (21,4 %)	8 (11,4 %)	
	Tibiofemoral stability	Front-back	Less than 5 mm	5-10 mm		10 + mm		
			43 (61%)	19 (27%)		8 (12%)		
		Medio-lateral	Less than 5 mm	5-10 mm		10 + mm		
			35 (50%)	24 (24%)		11 (16%)		
	Contracture	Flexible	5-10 gr	11-15 gr	16-20 gr	> 20 gr		
			52 (74,3%)	12 (17,1%)	4 (5,7%)	2 (2,9 %)		
writing		Not determined	< 10 gr	10 - 20 gr	> 20 gr			
		59 (84,3%)	11 (15,7%)	-	-			
Deviation line		Less than 5 gr	5-10 gr		Every 5 gr more			
		29 (41%)	38 (54%)		3 (5%)			
Functional evaluation	When walking		unlimited	>2km	1 – 2 km	< 1 km	to putin order	Can not walk
			23 (32,9%)	34 (48,5%)	11 (15,7%)	2 (2,9%)	- (-%)	-
	At the exit from the stairs		Number of steps	Easy up, hard down	Up and down hard	Easy down, hard up	Can't climb	
			7 (10%)	37 (52%)	13 (19%)	13 (19%)	-	
	Walk in the fixture		not using		With walking stick	With crutches	With crutches or on a wheelchair	
			28 (40%)		37 (52,9%)	5 (7,1%)	-	

Table 3 evaluates 70 patients in the main group of osteoarthritis of the knee joint based on the analysis of the results of clinical and functional indicators of the KSS scale. From the clinical indicators, the intensity of pain syndrome was assessed on the basis of the criteria "from mild pain to acute pain" and in the main group of patients were 5 (7.1%), 54 (77.2%) and 11 (15.7%). Preoperative results for the "stairs climbing" criterion confirmed the pain criteria.

Limitation of range of motion was found to be up to 15 degrees in 34 (48.6%) patients and up to 5 degrees in 2 (2.9%) patients with high levels of knee joint motion amplitude limitation.

In varus deformity osteoarthritis of the knee joint, the change in the biomechanical axis of the lower extremity resulted in a limitation of the amplitude of motion in the knee joint, especially when flexion contracture was observed in most cases. In 18 (25.7%) patients, "bending contracture" of 15-20 and >20 degrees of knee joint were detected, and in the remaining 52 (74.3%) patients, mild contracture - 5-10 degrees.

When evaluating the functional indicators, 33% of patients were indicated as "no walking limitation" on the criterion of "walking" before surgery, based on the criteria for walking more than 2 km - 48.6%, based on the criterion "restriction on walking" up to 1-2 km - 15.7% and the criterion "limit on walking" up to 1 km was 2.9%.

In addition, when evaluating the functional parameters of the knee joint on the criterion of "climbing stairs", 52% of patients indicated "easy to climb and difficult to descend", 19% indicated "difficult to climb and descend" and 19% "descending - easy, hard to climb" respectively.

According to the criterion "walking with the help of a device", 40% of patients indicated that they "do not use a walking device", 52.9% "walking with a cane or additional support devices" and 7.1% indicated as "walking with a crutch".

Knee joint function in varus deformity osteoarthritis of the knee joint was assessed on the basis of goniometric examination. The results obtained are presented in Table 4.

Table 4
Goniometric parameters in varus deformity osteoarthritis of the knee joint.

Knee joint movement volume (n=70)			P
Type of movement	Side	N gp.	
Bending	Healthy (n=70)	48,2±3,7°	<0.001*
	Level 2 DOA (n=32)	54,3±4,9°	
	Level 3 DOA (n=20)	62,8±6,2°	
	Flexible contracture of the knee joint (n=18)	82,4±10,2°	
Unbending	Healthy (n=70)	182,4±4,7°	<0.001
	Level 2 DOA (n=32)	178,1±3,8°	
	Level 3 DOA (n=20)	174,8±4,6°	
	Flexible contracture of the knee joint (n=18)	172,4±5,1°	

Knee joint movement amplitude (n=70)	N rp.	P
Healthy (n=70)	144,7±5,4°	
Level 2 DOA (n=32)	124,2±1,4°	<0.001
Level 3 DOA (n=20)	112,7±2,8°	<0.001
Flexible contracture of the knee joint (n=18)	90,3±5,8°	<0.001

Note: obtained results

As can be seen from Table 4, the normative values of movement volume in varus-modified deformable osteoarthritis showed different indicators with higher reliability than healthy knee joint movements. As mentioned above, a characteristic feature of varus deformity of the knee joint is a flexor contracture that occurs against the background of varus deformity of the knee joint. In the knee flexion criterion, the limitation of flexion movement compared to a healthy joint was 13% in grade II DOA and 30% in grade III DOA ($r < 0.002-0.01$). In 18 patients with advanced contracture of the knee joint, flexion restriction was 71% ($r < 0.001$) compared to a healthy joint.

According to the criteria of "movement amplitude" of the knee joint, the results obtained in 3 groups of 32 patients with grade II DOA, 20 patients with grade III DOA and 18 patients with advanced contracture of the knee joint were consistent with the results obtained on the criterion of "movement volume".

The study of changes in joint biomechanics in varus deformity of the knee joint is evaluated by determining the distance (Table 5)

Table 5

Healthy knee joints and joint opening angle indicators in deformable osteoarthritis (degrees)

The opening angle of the joint opening	Healthy joint	Knee joint DOA varus deformity	
	Average performance	Number of patients	Average performance
α — medial sphere	9,0 ± 0,30	70	5,77 ± 0,30
β — medial sphere	11,0 ± 0,33	70	11,82 ± 0,36

Note. The results obtained

As can be seen from Table 5, the opening angle of the joint opening is explained by the indicators α - medial area, β - lateral area. In healthy joints, the α -angle averaged 9.0 ± 0.30, the β -angle 11.0 ± 0.33 degrees, in the varus deformity of osteoarthritis of the knee joint, the α -angle averaged 5.77 ± 0.30, β -angle 11, 82 ± 0.36 degrees.

Table 6

Indicators of changes in the angles of the knee joint in normal and deforming osteoarthritis (degrees)

№	Indicators	Norm	Average performance	Change indicator
1	The index of the humerus of the femur	3,9–5,5	4,59 ± 0,05	3,17 ± 0,05
2	Large femur is the index of the intervertebral disc	5,0–6,4	5,61 ± 0,02	4,27 ± 0,04

3	The angle of the inner bone of the femur (α°)	20–26	23,28 $\pm$ 0,20	18,11 $\pm$ 0,10
4	The angle of the outer ridge of the femur ($\alpha 1^{\circ}$)	20–26	23,28 $\pm$ 0,20	23,68 $\pm$ 0,30
5	The angle of the inner femur of the greater femur (β°)	17–22	19,45 $\pm$ 0,16	17,26 $\pm$ 0,13
6	The large femur is the angle of the outer ridge ($\beta 1^{\circ}$)	17–22	19,45 $\pm$ 0,16	19,85 $\pm$ 0,18

Note. The results obtained

As can be seen from Table 6, in healthy varus deformity osteoarthritis of the knee joint, the healthy mean “index of the femoral fossa” varied from 4.59 ± 0.05 g to 3.17 ± 0.05 ($r < 0.002-0.01$). The calcaneal index of the tibia varied from 5.61 ± 0.02 g on average to 4.27 ± 0.04 g, and the angle of internal humerus of the femur (α°) changed to a healthy average of 23.28 ± 0.20 (r). < 0.001).

Conclusion: based on the above data, it should be noted that the deepening of degenerative-dystrophic processes in the knee joint, in turn, leads to an increase in the clinical manifestations of the disease, radiological changes and functional limitations of the knee joint.

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